

EU Cloud Edge IoT.eu
UNLOCK-CEI

Updated Risk Report

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D6.2 – Updated Risk Report

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EUCloudEdgeIoT	Short Name to refer to The European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum, an inter-project umbrella initiative of which UNLOCK CEI is a member
HE	Horizon Europe
IoT	Internet of Things
LSPs	Large Scale Pilots
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PM	Person Month
	Standard Development Organisation
SG	Stakeholder Group
UTM	Urchin Tracking Module
TF	Task Force
VCA	Value Chain Adopter
VP	Value Proposition
WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action

Keywords

Cloud-Edge-IoT; Computing; Continuum; Demand-Supply Dialogue; Communication; Engagement

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the key activities undertaken in quality and risk management for UNLOCK-CEI, including the identification, assessment and mitigation of risks, as well as the implementation of quality assurance and control. The updated risk register highlights the current risks at M30, and the mitigations strategies and actions taken throughout the project.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this deliverable

The purpose of Risk Management deliverables of UNLOCK-CEI were to prevent risks or minimize their impact in case they happened. To reach this, it was necessary that the consortium partners of the Project:

1. Clearly understood the risk management processes and roles
2. Knew key risks and quality expectations to incorporate in deliverables
3. Knew the process in response to issues
4. Had a full view of project level and WP level risks

To achieve this purpose, the D6.1 Risk Report provided an overview of the roles and processes to be implemented during the lifetime of the project, and complement them by a set of registers for guiding and monitoring execution.

This D6.2 Updated Risk Report deliverable provides an overview of:

- Roles and processes that were implemented during the lifetime of the project
- Set of registers for guiding and monitoring execution
- Risk Management activities throughout the project
- New Identified risks
- UNLOCK-CEI updated risk register
- Quality Management activities throughout the project

This deliverable also reports on the activities that were implemented from November 2022 to November 2024 regarding Risk and Quality Management.

1.2 Target audience

This document is elaborated for guidance of WP Leaders, Task Leaders and Project Coordinator.

1.3 How to use this report

This report updates the coordinated activities that were implemented to direct and control the project with regard to Quality and Risk Management.

2. Risk management approach

The project's Risk Management approach is designed to ensure potential and ongoing risks are identified, assessed, mitigated, and monitored throughout the lifecycle. For detailed information, please refer to D6.1 Risk Report, which contains a comprehensive description of the risk management process, roles and responsibilities.

2.1 Key elements of Risk Management

- Definition: A risk is an uncertain event or issue that may impact project objectives, measured by its likelihood and severity.
- Process:
 1. Identification: Monitoring for risks that could affect quality, time, or execution of tasks.
 2. Assessment: Evaluating risks based on their probability of occurrence and impact.
 3. Mitigation: Planning and implementing measures to address risks.
 4. Monitoring: Tracking risks and updating their status in the Risk Register.
 5. Responsibility: Clear roles for WP Leaders, Risk Manager, Project Manager, and Project Coordinator.
- Risk Evaluation Framework

The likelihood and severity of risks are evaluated using predefined criteria:

Table 1 - Level of risk likelihood and severity

Likelihood	Severity	Probability Scale
Very Low	Very Low	Less than 10%
Low	Low	Between 10% and 40%
Medium	Medium	Between 40% and 60%
High	High	Between 60% and 90%
Very High	Very High	More than 90%

- Governance and Responsibilities

The governance structure ensures risks are managed effectively:

- Risk Manager: Monitors the Risk Register, approves low-risk mitigation measures, and provides updates to the Project Manager.
- WP Leaders: Identify, evaluate, and address risks within their work packages.
- Project Manager: Oversees medium-risk mitigation measures in collaboration with the Project Management Board.
- Project Coordinator: Handles high-risk mitigation measures and liaises with the Project Management Board and EC/HADEA as necessary.
- Project Management Board: Approves medium and high-risk mitigation measures.

For a detailed breakdown of processes, roles, and responsibilities, please refer D6.1. Risk Report.

2.2 Overview of Risk Management activities throughout the project

2.2.1 Risk Management Tools

During the executing of the project, there were two different techniques that were implemented to ensure that the risks were identified and up to date which were:

1. Live risk register
2. An Action Points Checklist during the Consortium Meetings Agenda, detailing each action's status, deadline and responsible partner. Colour coded indicators were used to highlight the priority and importance of the items for quick and effective reference. This approach helped mitigate risks by enabling timely identification of priorities and potential delays.

Figure 1 – Action Points Checklist

2.2.2 New identified risks

During the lifetime of the project, five new risks were identified:

Table 2 – New identified risks

5	R14. Difficulties in collecting a sufficient number of cloud-edge-IoT user stories across all identified sectors, due to lack of maturity or readiness.	T5.3	3	2
6	R17. Data related to different WPs will be managed poorly.	T6.3	1	4
3	R18. Wave 1 Workshops delivered not sufficient data to capture service requirements	T2.2	5	4
2&3	R19. Misalignment of timing of T2.2 and T3.3 was an issue to have the required input of Market scenarios for wave 2 workshops.	T3.3	5	4
4	R20. Edge pilot factory is highly dependent on the maturity and market readiness of the CEI solutions developed in the metaOS RIAs and this a large physical workshop might not be a proper approach.	T4.3	5	4

3. Risk register

A Risk Register (see Annex 1: Updated UNLOCK-CEI Risk register) provided a record of identified risks related to the project, including their status, probability, and impact. It was implemented to capture and maintain information up to date on all the risks already identified. It acted as a guide for all stakeholders to visualize the impact and proximity, and to follow the mitigation measures in case of active and ongoing risks.

For each identified risk, the Risk Register detailed at least:

- Risk number
- Risk description

- Severity/Likelihood
- Mitigation Measures
- Risk Author
- Date Registered
- Risk owner
- Risk Status

WP	Risk Description	Task N°	Likelihood (1 low - 5 high)	Impact (1-low, 5-high)	Proposed Mitigation Measures	Risk Author	Date registered	Risk Status	Risk Owner	Actions taken
1	The survey results might not be ready by M6 for D1.1 due to the size of survey (700 interviews), its timeliness and the summer holidays in between.	T1.1	H	L	D1.1 will be generated based on the desk research and existig IDC studies on CEI adoption and market forecast. In the meanwhile, the survey will be designed and implemented and the results will be included in D1.2. In order to provide the input for T2.2 on time, the results of survey will be shared by partners as soon as they will be ready.	Golboo Poursabdollahi-an	24.06.2022	Under-control	IDC	Survey is designed and on generated based on the de
1	The interviews for business opportunities analysis might not be completely aligned with the identified service requirements in WP2 due to scheduling of the tasks	T1.2	M	M	There will be revisioning iterations of interview guidelines in T1.2. A first guideline will be designed for the initial interviews and then regularly the guideline will be revised based on the input that will be generated in WP2.	Golboo Poursabdollahi-an	21.11.2022	Under-control	IDC	
2	The Adoption Readiness Framework focuses mostly on qualitative data instead of a balanced set of qualitative/quantitative data.	T2.1	3	3	There will be revisioning of the whole process to simplify the procedure and to make informed decisions to convert data gathering from qualitative analysis to quantative analysis.	Ella Bellussi	22.11.2022	Under-control	EGI	

Figure 2 - Screenshot of active Risk Register in UNLOCK-CEI

3.1 UNLOCK-CEI updated identified risks

Risks can, and should, be identified at any time during the delivery of the project. This helps to understand the specific objectives that are at risk and to formulate an appropriate risk management.

After the identification of a risk, the next step was to assess the probability and impact of each risk and plan the response. The response step involved identifying and evaluating the appropriate risk response to remove or reduce the impact of the risk. It was important that the risk response was proportional to the risk. The table 2 below includes the updated detailed identified risks for the project, the likelihood and impact for each one and the work packages involved. The table 3 below presents an updated risk visualisation that maps the likelihood of an event occurring against its potential impact, helping to prioritise risks based on their severity and probability. From November 2022 to November 2024, five additional risks were identified by WP LEADERS. The proposed mitigation measures to implement in case such risks occur are detailed in Annex 1: Updated UNLOCK-CEI Risk register.

Table 3- Updated Detailed risks and mitigation actions

WP	Risk Description	Task N°	Likelihood	Impact
1	R1. The survey results might not be ready by M6 for D1.1 due to the size of survey (700 interviews), its timeliness and the summer holidays in between.	T1.1	5	1
1	R2. The interviews for business opportunities analysis might not be completely aligned with the identified service requirements in WP2 due to scheduling of the tasks	T1.2	3	3
2	R3. The Adoption Readiness Framework focuses mostly on qualitative data instead of a balanced set of qualitative/quantitative data.	T2.1	3	3

2	R4. Service Requirements and Market Scenarios are based on limited and biased datasets.	T.2.2	3	3
3	R5. Problems with recruiting experts for the value chain adopter groups	T.3.1	5	3
3	R6. Input from WP2 is not delivered on time, lack of validation results	T 3.2	5	3
3	R7. Input from WP2 is not delivered on time, lack of validation results	T 3.3	5	3
4	R8. RIA technologies are too immature for market analysis and/or unfit for engagement	T4.1	2	4
4	R9. Readiness adoption framework does not map onto commercial feasibility framework	T 4.2	2	4
4	R10. Commercial actors within the Value Chain Adopters groups do not provide the required input	T 4.2	2	2
4	R11. Low engagement of external actors and commercial entities in piloting and partnering opportunities	T4.3	3	5
5	R12. There is a possibility that the initial delivery of the full usable version of the joint eucloudedgeiot.eu or other initial joint communication outputs are completed later than initially planned due to coordination needs with Open Continuum and the EC	T5.1	5	1
5	R13. There is a risk of Low participation / engagement at events (in presence or remotely, in general or considering specific stakeholder groups) especially if these are many and scheduled closely to each other	T5.3	3	3
5	R14. Difficulties in collecting a sufficient number of cloud-edge-IoT user stories across all identified sectors, due to lack of maturity or readiness.	T5.3	3	2
6	R15. Inadequate management and deviations.	T6.1	1	4
6	R16. Deliverables not submitted/ completed on time	T6.2	1	4
6	R17. Data related to different WPs will be managed poorly.	T6.3	1	4
3	R18. Wave 1 Workshops delivered not sufficient data to capture service requirements	T2.2	5	4
2&3	R19. Misalignment of timing of T2.2 and T3.3 was an issue to have the required input of Market scenarios for wave 2 workshops.	T3.3	5	4
4	R20. Edge pilot factory is highly dependent on the maturity and market readiness of the CEI solutions developed in the metaOS RIAs and this a large physical workshop might not be a proper approach.	T4.3	5	4

Table 4- Updated Risks visualization of likelihood against impact

High	1, 12	5, 6, 7	11, 18, 19, 20
Medium	14	2, 3, 4, 13	
Low	10	8,9	15, 16, 17
Likelihood / Impact	Low	Medium	High

4. Quality Management Approach

4.1 UNLOCK-CEI Approach

In UNLOCK-CEI, Quality Management was referred to the coordinated activities to direct and control the project to ensure quality of the activities and inputs of the project.

This section provides an overview of the quality roles and processes that were implemented during the execution of the UNLOCK-CEI project. It was complemented by a set of registers for guiding and monitoring.

The quality process was established to ensure that all the work carried out during the different stages of project would be delivered with the expected quality. It had most emphasis on Quality Control checks to be applied throughout the preparation of a deliverable.

4.2 Deliverable Quality Review

At the beginning of the project a quality criterion for each deliverable was defined. The Quality Criteria gave to all the partners a description of the quality specification that every deliverable must meet and the quality measurements that would be applied during the lifetime of the project.

Each deliverable had four different people responsible for its Quality Management:

1. WP Leader:
 - Defined the Quality criteria of deliverables
 - Approved Table of Content
2. Producer: The person responsible for developing the deliverable who oversaw for:
 - Delivering the Table of Content, which would be approved by the WP Leader
 - Producing content, according to the schedule
 - Ensuring the overall quality of the content
3. Reviewer 1: A person (different than the producer) who assessed whether a deliverable met the quality expectations. It was also the person who was authorized to approve a deliverable as being complete:
 - Checked that content matched the description in the Description of Action (DoA).
 - Checked that content met the outcomes defined in quality criteria.
 - Reviewed the document to ensure completeness and accuracy.
 - Cannot be directly involved in drafting the deliverable.
 - Once all checks were performed, provided final approval.

4. Reviewer 2: A person independent of the producer who assessed whether a deliverable met the quality expectations
- Checked that content met outcomes defined in quality criteria.
 - Performed language review.
 - Completed approval checklist.

Figure 3 - UNLOCK-CEI Quality review process

4.3 Quality management tools and resources

During the execution of the project, there were two different tools that ensured that the deliverables met the Quality Criteria. These were:

1. Quality register (see Annex 2: Updated Quality register) was available for every consortium partner in the project repository (WP6. Project ManagementàT6.2 Risk and Quality Managementà Quality & Risk registers) and it was used to summarise all the deliverables that were planned and provided information of dates, responsibilities, and quality criteria and included:
 - List of reviewers: The Quality Register already defined the responsible, reviewer and dates for each deliverable to be submitted according the project schedule.
 - Specific quality criteria checklist

Figure 4 - Screenshot of active Quality Register

2. Deliverable acceptance checklist: a prioritised list of criteria that the deliverable must meet before the approval of the reviewer. (see **Error! Reference source not found.**)

5. Overview of risk and quality management activities

To ensure that both Risk and Quality management were updated and that the processes were implemented effectively, a few steps were established and carried out during the execution of the project:

1. **Communication:** As part of Risk and Quality Management activities, there was an additional step for communication. Communication was undertaken continually. This step ensured that the information related to risks and quality was up to date as the project exposure to risk was never static. To ensure correct communication, the following activities were carried out:
 - Risk management: during the monthly Consortium Meetings, if a new risk was identified or the status of an existing risk was modified by a WP Leader a risk section was included in the WP presentation and identified risks would be updated or new risks would be pointed out. After these meetings, the Risk Manager will communicate with WP Leaders in order to assess the risks and update the register in case if necessary.
 - Quality management: a reminder for the Quality Process and responsibilities was included in every Consortium Meeting ensuring that every responsible person was aware of their tasks regarding this matter. Also, a table with dates and tasks was included at the end of every Consortium Meetings as a reminder. The Quality Manager would communicate with WP Leaders in case of deviations with the dates established in the process.

Figure 5 - Screenshot of Next Deliverables reminder in Consortium Meetings

2. **Review:** Every 3 months, the processes were reviewed to ensure that all the persons involved knew their tasks and to ensure that the established processes were being efficient. Additionally, all the tools were reviewed. This review was carried out by the Risk and Quality Manager. No modification of the processes was made.
3. **Update:** After every Consortium Meeting, the Risk and Quality Manager updated the register, to ensure that all the information was up to date. In addition, in case of modifications and identification of new risks between Consortium Meetings, the Risk and Quality Manager immediately updated all the registers and communicated to every person involved in the process.

6. Key learnings

This section outlines insights gained during the execution of both Quality & Risk Management and provide key learnings, highlighting improvements in responsiveness, communication, and accountability, as well as opportunities for enhancing the risk and quality management to support project execution.

1. **Focused Action Points Checklist Over Risk-Only Review:** Shifting from a dedicated risk section planned in D6.1 to an action points checklist streamlined the focus on day-to-day execution. This change allowed the team to address actionable items with higher priority while still capturing essential risk insights when needed.
2. **Effective Deliverable Reminders:** The regular reminder of deliverables during consortium meetings was beneficial in keeping the team involved in elaboration and review of deliverables aligned and ensuring timely submissions, reinforcing accountability and adherence to deadlines.
3. **Clear Understanding of Roles and Processes:** As the team became familiar with roles and processes, collaboration improved, allowing for efficient execution of tasks and a smoother risk management workflow.
4. **Deliverable Submission Process:** Although deliverables were consistently submitted for review, they often arrived with less time than requested. This indicates an opportunity to strengthen planning and time management within the submission process.
5. **Risk Identification and Communication Workflow:** The process for identifying and escalating new risks (to the risk manager, project manager, and then project coordinator) ensured that risks were promptly managed and documented. This workflow also led to a successful amendment, showing the process's effectiveness in adapting to evolving risks.

6. Risk Register Updates: Opting to update the risk register only when WP leaders communicate significant changes or new risks has proven to be efficient, maintaining relevance without the need for redundant updates after every consortium meeting.

Annex 1: Updated UNLOCK-CEI Risk register

WP	Risk Description	Task N°	Likelihood (1 low - 5 high)	Impact (1-low, 5 - high)	Proposed Mitigation Measures	Risk Author	Date registered	Risk Status	Risk Owner	Actions taken
1	R1. The survey results might not be ready by M6 for D1.1 due to the size of survey (700 interviews), its timeliness and the summer holidays in between.	T1.1	5	1	D1.1 will be generated based on the desk research and existing IDC studies on CEI adoption and market forecast. In the meanwhile, the survey will be designed and implemented and the results will be included in D1.2. In order to provide the input for T2.2 on time, the results of survey will be shared by partners as soon as they will be ready.	Golboo Pourabdollahian	24.06.2022	Under-control	IDC	Survey is designed and ongoing. D1.1 is generated based on the desk research
1	R2. The interviews for business opportunities analysis might not be completely aligned with the identified service requirements in WP2 due to scheduling of the tasks	T1.2	3	3	There will be revisioning iterations of interview guidelines in T1.2. A first guideline will be designed for the initial interviews and then regularly the guideline will be revised based on the input that will be generated in WP2.	Golboo Pourabdollahian	21.11.2022	Under-control	IDC	

2	R3. The Adoption Readiness Framework focuses mostly on qualitative data instead of a balanced set of qualitative/quantitative data.	T2.1	3	3	There will be revisioning of the whole process to simplify the procedure and to make informed decisions to convert data gathering from qualitative analysis to quantitative analysis.	Elia Bellussi	22.11.2022	Under-control	EGI	The risk was identified before completing the framework. Ultimately, the framework was developed focusing on both quantitative and qualitative data.
2	R4. Service Requirements and Market Scenarios are based on limited and biased datasets.	T.2.2	3	3	There will be revisioning of the whole selection process to better understand which one should be used and how to manage the projection for each scenario.	Elia Bellussi	22.11.2022	Under-control	EGI	Additional information sources have been considered to mitigate the risk.
3	R5. Problems with recruiting experts for the value chain adopter groups	T.3.1	5	3	In D3.1, the relevant data-driven value chains from the five sectors were selected. Based on the analysis of the strategic research and innovation agendas, the determine the main CEI motivating drivers were derived. We identified and described the value chains with the central stakeholders for	Inessa Seifert	21.11.2022	Under-control	VDE-VDI	

					<p>each sector. The structure of the value chains will be used to recruit the experts for the experts. Together with our partner TrustIT, we set up a registration form for the recruitment of experts that is now circulating in the social networks and further dissemination channels, There will be a revision of the invitation to join the value chain adopter groups with concrete dates for the planned workshops. The workshop results provide input to the WP 2 and WP 1.</p>					
3	R6. Input from WP2 is not delivered on time, lack of validation results	T 3.2	5	3	<p>We will employ the input from WP1 with the survey results regarding business drivers and use cases that facilitate the adoption of CEI technologies to motivate the experts for participation in the workshops. We need the input from WP 2 that covers preliminary service offerings and methodology for interaction with the stakeholders. We will approach WP2 leaders and set up a series of meetings to be prepared for the workshops.</p>	Inessa Seifert	21.11.2022	Under-control	VDE-VDI	

3	R7. Input from WP2 is not delivered on time, lack of validation results	T 3.3	5	3	Due to lack of D2.2 market structures and scenarios (in terms of technical capabilities and business arrangements), we analysed already existing solutions and interviewed the solution providers regarding possible market pathways and scenarios for the Large Scale Pilots.	Inessa Seifert	21.11.2022	Under-control	VDE-VDI	
4	R8. RIA technologies are too immature for market analysis and/or unfit for engagement	T4.1	2	4	Early mapping of the project outputs will provide a realistic understanding of potential maturity. The results of the project will be continuously monitored and a maturity assessment applied to ensure correct fit.	Brendan Rowan	24.11.2022		BLU	
4	R9. Readiness adoption framework does not map onto commercial feasibility framework	T 4.2	2	4	Frameworks are to be developed in parallel with close coordination between WP4 and WP2 to ensure resulting methodologies are aligned and relevant	Jose Enrique Alvarez	22.11.2022	Under-control	BLU	Direct participation in development of frameworks and methodologies with parallel development

4	R10. Commercial actors within the Value Chain Adopters groups do not provide the required input	T4.2	2	2	We will employ the results from T3.2 to base our following tasks on developing the CEI Tech Commercial Feasibility and that task required the inputs from T 2.1 and we all need to have more clarity in the Readiness Framework and the methodology used to deliver that work package is key. If required, independent consultations will be made with relevant actors to complement and confirm results.	Jose Enrique Alvarez	22.11.2022	Under-control	BLU	
4	R11. Low engagement of external actors and commercial entities in piloting and partnering opportunities	T4.3	3	5	Relevant actors will be sourced through the activities of WP3, the members of RIA consortia and through the industry associations of which the consortium partners are members.	Brendan Rowan	24.11.2022	Under-control	BLU	

5	R12. There is a possibility that the initial delivery of the full usable version of the joint eucloudedgeiot.eu or other initial joint communication outputs are completed later than initially planned due to coordination needs with Open Continuum and the EC	T5.1	5	1	A temporary landing page has been in place since the project kick-off to handle the main information and communications. Additional temporary web pages will be created ad hoc to promote specific actions, e.g. the first Leveraging also on other already active channels, such as social media, no significant negative effects are expected in case of website delivery delay	Maria Giuffrida	30.06.2022	Under-control	TRUST IT	Preliminary landing page online since M01, monthly calls for TF6 since July 2022 (M02), continuous update and improvement via regular meetings with partners, the TFs and the EC, Complementary dissemination actions via social media channels and newsletters
5	R13. There is a risk of Low participation / engagement at events (in presence or remotely, in general or considering specific stakeholder groups) especially if these are many and scheduled closely to each other	T5.3	3	3	The project will need to deliver many events both in presence and remotely. To ensure high level of participation and engagement of all needed stakeholder groups a set of actions will be implemented: promotional material with clear stakeholder-specific messaging and value propositions, leverage on sector and stakeholder-specific multipliers,	Maria Giuffrida	30.09.2022	Under-control	TRUST IT	Dedicated promotional material, early promotion, targeted messages. Results are positive with Average of 100+ registered participants per event and average of

					scheduling of events in a way that adequate planning is possible and there is no cannibalisation effect, initiating promotion in advance, paid campaigns					50+ live attendants
5	R14. Difficulties in collecting a sufficient number of cloud-edge-IoT user stories across all identified sectors, due to lack of maturity or readiness.	T5.3	3	2	Engage more proactively with the industrial partners of the research and innovation projects. Consider offering incentives or recognition (e.g. visibility) for valuable contributions to encourage more participation.	Maria Giuffrida	01.08.2023	Under-control	TRUST IT	Success stories were collected joining forces with R&I projects in the MetaOS cluster. The industrial partners involved in the most mature and promising use cases, as determined also via the CEI-LING tool. The KPI for success stories production has been met and exceeded

6	R15. Inadequate management and deviations.	T6.1	1	4	The proposed coordinator has extensive experience in EC-funded projects. The management structures & procedures will ensure a close supervision of delivery of the expected results. Project meetings will take place regularly and will identify and isolate potential problems and react early. Bi-weekly technical meetings are set up to follow up the progress of different WPs and required interaction among WPs. The meeting frequency will be further increased should critical situations arise. The WP Leaders, and ultimately the coordinator, will impose specific corrective actions on the overall 36-month project workplan.	Golboo Pourabdollahian	01.06.2022	Under-control	IDC	
6	R16. Deliverables not submitted/ completed on time	T6.2	1	4	Risk and quality processes are set up with clear deadlines and roles and responsibilities with enough time-span to take corrective actions for deliverables in case needed.	Brendan Rowan	01.06.2022	Under-control	BLU	
6	R17. Data related to different WPs will be managed poorly.	T6.3	1	4	A specific data management plan will be delivered by end of M6 providing all the processes to ensure proper	Golboo Pourabdollahian		Under-control	IDC	

					management of data and defining all the data sets and their specifications. The data management plan is a live document and will be updated during the project if needed.					
3	R18. Wave 1 Workshops delivered not sufficient data to capture service requirements		5	4	After the workshops, in-depth interviews with selected experts allowed to fill the gaps in the collected data regarding value, data and revenue streams in the value chains and networks.	Inessa Seifert	13.09.2023	Under-control	VDE-VDI	
2&3	R19. Misalignment of timing of T2.2 and T3.3 was an issue to have the required input of Market scenarios for wave 2 workshops.	T3.3	5	4	The timing is revised in the amendment (due time for D3.3 moved to M24) and since major part of the deliverable will be related to market scenarios and pathways related to T2.3 which is led by EGI the ownership is moved to EGI.	EGI	13.09.2023	Under-control	EGI	The due date for deliverable D3.3 has been shifted to month 24. Regular meetings and progress check-ins between teams has been hold.
4	R20. Edge pilot factory is highly dependent on the maturity and market readiness of the CEI solutions developed in the metaOS RIAs and this a large physical workshop might not be a proper approach.	T4.3	5	4	Given that the next funding round for CEI IAs and RIAs is in March, greater impact will be achieved through more curated sessions that are delivered earlier than originally planned.	Golboo Pourabdollahian		Under-control	IDC	

Annex 2: Updated Quality register

					Definition of done		
Deliverable N°	Deliverable title	Deadline	Intended public	Expected use by the intended public	Completeness	Relevance	Timeliness
D1.1	Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape	11/30/2022	Project Policy Solution providers (in particular projects) Value chain adopters Partners Makers supply	Understanding the main dimensions of CEI landscape and the evolution of CEI Understanding the CEI technology landscape in terms of the market status quo and forecast Gain knowledge about the CEI use-cases in the selected 5 verticals Gain knowledge about the main market factors impacting the CEI market (drivers and barriers)	Covers the status quo and forecast of Cloud-Edge and IoT market Covers the 5 selected verticals Includes the list of use-cases per vertical in the survey Provide a summary of existing drivers and barriers based on a desk research	Is readily understandable to both commercial and technology developers Is able to provide a backbone for the WP2,3,4	Forecast for 5 years
D1.2	Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape	5/31/2023		Understand the adoption level of CEI technologies in 5 selected verticals across 7 member states Gain knowledge about the most relevant use-cases of CEI in each vertical and the driver and barriers for the adoption Be able to use the demand landscape analysis to develop the solutions according to market needs Gain knowledge about the main business opportunities in CEI landscape Gain knowledge about main CEI ecosystems and the competitiveness	Covers the results of the survey for 5 verticals in 7 member states Includes the top 3 use-cases per vertical Includes the results of the interviews in terms of main business opportunities and CEI ecosystems	Is readily understandable to both commercial and technology developers Applicable to adopters groups and technology providers	Forecast for 5 years

				Use the report to identify potential market opportunities to target in the upcoming years			
D1.3	Cloud-Edge-IoT Demand Landscape	5/31/2024		Understand the CEI demand-supply dynamics Gain knowledge about the main gaps between demand and supply Use insights and recommendations to fill the gap and accelerate the exploitation of solutions to the market	Covers the supply landscape provided by the Supply project Includes the main gaps between demand and supply Include a set of insights and recommendations	Able to guide the supply projects to adjust their solutions based on market needs	Insights will be applicable for projects developing solutions to launch within the next 4 years
D2.1	Readiness Framework and Service Requirements	5/31/2023	Project Partners Value Chain Adopters Industry Technology Developers Technology Providers Research and Innovation Organisations Technology Associations Research Centres Universities Business Users	Creating the basis for understanding the market development for both supply and demand related to the CEI landscape to create a breakthrough into in the evolutionary scenarios of the use of such technologies.	Covering the foundations for understanding the theories behind the development of consumption for such technologies.	Understandable methodology to address market readiness for stakeholders.	Forecast for 4 years but adaptable to the changes

D2.2	Preliminary Market Scenarios & Pathways to the Future Open European CEI Ecosystem	11/30/2023	Project Partners Value Chain Adopters Industry Technology Developers Technology Providers Research and Innovation Organisations Technology Associations Research Centres Universities Business Users	Understanding the market development for both supply and demand related to the CEI landscape to create a breakthrough into in the evolutionary scenarios of the use of such technologies.	Covering the results of the analysis done with the framework to focus on delivering results to stakeholders.	Understandable projection of the objectives for such technologies.	Forecast for 4 years but adaptable to the changes
D2.3	Final Position Paper on the future Open European CEI Ecosystem	11/30/2024	Policy Makers	Describing the current scenario and how the project will tackle it to develop a consistent innovation.	Reporting the results to the stakeholders to explain the outcomes.	Able to guide stakeholders in their strategic decisions.	Forecast for 4 years but adaptable to the changes
D3.1	CEI Ecosystems overview with the value chain adopters groups	11/30/2022	Project Partners Policy Makers Value chain adopters Technology Developers Technology Providers	Understanding the major CEI stakeholders and the ecosystem. Overview about the data driven value chains for the further analysis regarding gaps, business opportunities, vendor lock-ins and the flow of the revenue streams.	Covering the overview of the stakeholders in the target domains, understanding who are the demand-pull drivers in the data driven value chains.	Able to organize the dialogue with the relevant target stakeholders in the value chain adopter groups. Able to provide input for WP2 for refining of the taxonomies.	Forecast for 3 years, since the stakeholder landscape is currently very dynamic.

D3.2	Revised structure for CEI Service Requirements	5/31/2023	Project Partners Value Chain Adopters Industry Technology Developers Technology Providers Research and Innovation Organisations Technology Associations Research Centres Universities Business Users	Including insights from the first sector specific workshop wave: outcomes of the blue ocean strategy - the market segmentation, the business drivers and the business opportunities for new players in the ecosystem.	Explaining the views of the experts regarding the service criteria, gaps and conditions for uptake of CEI technologies.	Able to identify the market structures: the relevant stakeholders and their current offerings on the market. Providing hints to the gaps and impediments.	Forecast for 3-5 years but also adaptable to changes
D3.3	Report on CEI Service Requirements	11/30/2023	Project Partners Value Chain Adopters Industry Technology Developers Technology Providers Research and Innovation Organisations Technology Associations Business Users	Including insights from the second sector specific workshop wave: validation of the Market Scenarios & Pathways to the Future Open European CEI Ecosystem by the experts: "dos" and "don'ts".	Explaining the views of the experts regarding make or buy discussions and more concrete requirements on service offerings.	Able to identify the gaps and business opportunities, provide guidance for the future developments.	Forecast for 3-5 years but also adaptable to changes
D4.1	Technology scoping paper	11/30/2022	Project Partners Policy Makers Value chain adopters	Understanding the CEI technology development landscape Gain a clear definition of the technologies and solutions under development Scope the role of the EU CEI initiative and potential market offering Be able to identify the technology development roadmap, interdependencies and maturity timelines	Covers all technologies developed under the CEI, NGIoT and HCloud Initiatives Provides key uses cases for demonstration Provides a defined limit/scope of CEI technologies	Is able to guide the discussions within WP2 and WP3 Is readily understandable to both commercial and technology developers	Provides mapping of the tech development of the next 5 years Delivered in advance of key framework developments

D4.2	Commercial Feasibility Tool	11/30/2023	Technology developers	<p>Analysis of their technology maturity and position themselves on a map towards market readiness</p> <p>Define their position on the value chain and key potential customers</p> <p>Identify their customers needs and demands</p> <p>Understand the changes that will be required to the their solution to increase adoptability</p> <p>Use as the basis of their Go To Market strategy</p>	Covers 5 key value chains/markets	Applicable to all CEI technologies (software/hardware/platform forms, etc.)	Useful life of 3 years
D4.3	Pilot factory outcomes	5/31/2024	Policy Makers	<p>Review of key concepts and applications of interest</p> <p>Understand commercial appetite for CEI technologies</p>	Provides a summary of all concepts developed in the pilot factory	Makes links between priority concepts and value chains for uptake	Maps pilots out on a 12-month implementation period
D4.4	Market developments learnings	9/30/2024	Industry - Technology directors Policy Makers	<p>Identify the main gaps between market demands and tech maturity</p> <p>Understand where key failures have or may occur</p> <p>Prepare strategies and structures to overcome gaps</p>	<p>Includes specific examples where tech and market did not match</p> <p>Provides actionable recommendations for both industry adopters, tech developers and policy makers</p>	<p>Learnings will apply to commercial contexts</p> <p>Learnings will inform the development of future funding programmes</p>	<p>Recommendations will be applicable to market ready technologies and 5 years of roadmap development</p>
D5.1	Communications, dissemination and engagement plan	8/31/2022	Business Users, Industrial and Technology Associations, Tech providers and developers, research and innovation organisations, policy makers and other facilitators	<p>Understand how the project plans to target the main stakeholders, build a community and produce tangible impact, Understand the branding and positioning of the project in the wider EUCloudEdgeIoT umbrella initiative</p>	<p>Describes the intended plan for communication, dissemination and engagement activities, details relevant KPIs for communication and how they support the project KPIs, identifies the main stakeholder groups and their value proposition, channels</p>	<p>Provides a guidance for the communication and dissemination strategy to implement in order to build an engaged community of stakeholders</p>	Covers the whole project

					used and messaging to target them		
D5.2	1st Updated Communications, dissemination and engagement plan	11/30/2023	Business Users, Industrial and Technology Associations, Tech providers and developers, research and innovation organisations, policy makers and other facilitators	Provides an update to the previous Communication and Engagement plan detailing intermediate results achieved by the project on the main activities and KPIs	Provides a description of all activities performed with related results to date, provides explanations for any deviations from the original plan and provides an update on the plan for the remaining activities based on lessons learned in the first half of the project	Provides preliminary tangible results on the community engaged and impact generated	Covers the whole project, with a main focus on the first half
D5.3	2nd Updated Communications, dissemination and engagement plan	11/30/2024	Business Users, Industrial and Technology Associations, Tech providers and developers, research and innovation organisations, policy makers and other facilitators	Provides the final results and impact of the communication, dissemination and engagement activities, allows understanding the success of the envisioned plan	Provides a review of all activities performed, results achieved and comments on the performance obtained on communication, dissemination and engagement aspects	Provides tangible results on the community engaged and impact generated at the end of the project	Covers the whole project, with a main focus on the second half
D5.4	EU Demand side Radar	5/31/2023	Business Users, Tech Providers	Provides preliminary landscape radar results including demand side overview	Describes methodology for performing the landscape and radar, provides an overview of demand landscape with concrete examples and	Provides up to date information on the demand use cases, and represents a possible source of best practices	Covers the first half of the project

					interprets preliminary results and possible gaps		
D5.5	Updated EU Demand side Radar	9/30/2024	Business Users, Tech Providers	Provides the final landscape radar results including demand side overview	Provides an overview of demand landscape with concrete examples, interprets final results and possible gaps, compares updated version with preliminary version in D5.4	Provides up to date information on the demand use cases, and represents a possible source of best practices	Covers the second half of the project
D5.6	User stories and policy briefs booklet	11/30/2023	Policy Makers	Provides a collection of user stories and policy briefs published and disseminated in the first half of the project.	Describes stories, synthesises key learning points, success factors, challenges overcome, translates these insights into policy recommendations	Identifies CEI adopters success factors and priorities for policy making	Covers the first half of the project
D5.7	Updated User stories and policy briefs booklet	9/30/2024	Policy Makers	Provides a collection of user stories and policy briefs published and disseminated in the second half of the project.	Describes stories, synthesises key learning points, success factors, challenges overcome, translates these insights into policy recommendations	Identifies CEI adopters success factors and priorities for policy making	Covers the second half of the project
D5.8	Sustainability plan	11/30/2023	Project Partners, EC, Policy makers	Summarises all major results, KERs, exploitation opportunities and future funding scenarios for the generated assets, based on preliminary results	KERs, accessibility of KERs, future use and exploitation options	Proves the sustainability of the project	Covers the whole project

D5.9	Updated Sustainability plan	11/30/2024	Project Partners, EC, Policy makers	Updates all major results, KERs, exploitation opportunities and future funding scenarios for the generated assets, based on final results	KERs, accessibility of KERs, future use and exploitation options	Proves the sustainability of the project	Covers the whole project and the next 12 to 24 months
D6.1	Risk Report	11/30/2022	Project Partners Coordinator	Understand clearly all the risk management processes and roles Know key risks and quality expectations to incorporate in delivery Consult in response to issues Have a full view of project level and WP level risks	Includes at least 2 risks for each WP	Processes are practical and applicable	Provides forecast into the next 24 months
D6.2	Updated Risk Report	11/30/2024	Project Partners	Identify key learnings Adapt future activities and project design	Includes at least 2 risks for each WP	Processes are practical and applicable	Covers the whole project
D6.3	Data Management Plan	11/30/2022		Understanding the methods and approaches for data collection and curation during and after the project Understanding the approached to manage data and standards to apply	Includes the data sharing and managing guidelines for all partners Includes guidelines of data ownership for all partners	Processes are practical and applicable	Provides forecast into the next 12 months
D6.4	Updated Data Management Plan	11/30/2024		Identify key learnings Adapt future activities for data management	Includes the data sharing and managing guidelines for all partners Includes guidelines of data ownership for all partners	Processes are practical and applicable	Covers the whole project

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